

D6.1 Initial Communication, Dissemination and Standardisation Plan

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Control sheet

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1. Introduction

1.1. Althena concept and approach

Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions have emerged thanks to novel Artificial Intelligence (AI) which can be trained with huge amounts of data to produce driving functions with better-than-human performance under certain conditions. The race on AI keeps on building HW/SW frameworks to manage and process even larger real and synthetic datasets to train increasingly accurate AI models.

However, AI remains largely unexplored with respect to explainability (interpretability of model functioning), privacy preservation (exposure of sensitive data), ethics (bias and wanted/unwanted behaviour), and accountability (responsibilities of AI outputs). These features will establish the basis of trustworthy AI, as a novel paradigm to fully understand and trust AI in operation, while using it at its full capabilities for the benefit of society.

AITHENA will contribute to build Explainable AI (XAI) in CCAM development and testing frameworks, researching three main AI pillars: data (real/synthetic data management), models (data fusion, hybrid AI approaches), and testing (physical/virtual XiL set-ups with scalable MLOps).

A human-centric methodology will be created to derive trustworthy AI dimensions from user identified group needs in CCAM applications. AITHENA will innovate proposing a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) on XAI, and an analysis to explore trade-offs between these dimensions.

Demonstrators will show the AITHENA methodology in four critical use cases: perception (what does the AI perceive, and why), situational awareness (what is the AI understanding about the current driving environment, including the driver state), decision (why a certain decision is taken), and traffic management (how transport-level applications interoperate with AI-enabled systems operating at vehicle-level).

Created data and tools will be made available via European data sharing initiatives (OpenData and OpenTools) to foster research on trustworthy AI for CCAM.

1.2. Athena consortium

The AITHENA consortium consists of 17 partners from 6 different EU countries (and an associated partner from Switzerland) who gather all the necessary background and expertise to achieve the objectives of the project. Furthermore, as a Research and Innovation Action (RIA), a balance mix of partners has been selected for provisioning the research, expertise and technology required to meet the project objectives:

- research partners (VICOM, IKA, TUE, VIF, TNO, BUW),
- technology providers (TTTA, IFAG, SIE-NL, SIE-BE),
- industry (CAF, MAPTM, IDI, RC, VALEO),
- Social Science (TUE) and
- stakeholder associations (IRU, FIA).

To ensure the value of the project results are maximized, the symbiosis of research, technology and business will enable AITHENA to demonstrate direct relevance to European society and industry.

Figure 1 Distribution of AITHENA partners

1.3. Purpose of this deliverable

This deliverable is intended to present an initial communication, dissemination, and standardisation plan. An updated version of the plan will be provided in M18 in deliverable D6.6. All activities within the implementation of the AITHENA project relevant to tasks: T6.1, T6.2 and T6.3 will be reported in deliverable D6.5, due in M36.

The main objective of the AITHENA initial communication, dissemination, and standardisation plan is:

- To develop key, targeted messages to different technical, scientific, industry and policy audiences.

- To define channels, dissemination opportunities, such events and scientific publications and networking activities to communicate the project and disseminate widely project results, outcomes, and achievements whenever available.

This deliverable also prepares the basis for all activities in WP6 related to communication, dissemination, and standardisation. However, the focus of this deliverable as well as future update (M18) is to set the foundations for the three tasks:

- Task 6.1 Communication strategy.
- Task 6.2 Scientific and industrial dissemination and standardisation.
- Task 6.3 End user dissemination.

The current version of this deliverable is related to *T6.1 Communication strategy [M1-M5]* which coordinates the work in *WP6 – IMPACT: Exploitation, Dissemination and Standardisation [M1-M36]* and monitors the progress in accordance with the AITHENA project timeline. Additionally, T6.1 will continuously liaise with other WPs to ensure alignment of the projects output to be disseminated.

The remaining tasks relevant for this deliverable: Task 6.2 and Task 6.3 will be presented in detail in the updated version of this deliverable (D6.6, due in M18). This is because at the time of writing this deliverable, *Task 6.2 Scientific and industrial dissemination and standardisation* has just started (M6) and *Task 6.3 End user dissemination* will start at later stage of the AITHENA implementation (M13). Task 6.2 will connect the AITHENA project's results and achievements with relevant scientific and industrial fora as well as events to disseminate the tools and knowledge generated in the project to expert audiences.

Task 6.3 will be focused on preparation and implementation of an information campaign which aims to educate users about the use cases developed in the project and to promote advantages of XAI in CCAM can bring to the users.

1.4. Structure of this deliverable

This report firstly presents the consortium, work plan in WP6 and corresponding tasks, and interactions between WP6 and remaining WPs. Secondly it describes communication, dissemination and standardisation activities, channels, tools, and measures that will be used throughout the lifetime of the project.

2. Work Package 6 - work plan and responsibilities

Task No	Task Title	Task Leader	Task Duration
6.1	Communication strategy	FIA	M1-M5
6.2	Scientific and industrial dissemination and standardisation	VALEO	M6-M36
6.3	End user dissemination	FIA	M13-M36
6.4	OpenData plan and OpenTool plan and sharing	VICOM	M17-M36
6.5	Lessons learned and policy recommendations	RC	M22-M36
6.6	Exploitation & commercialisation plan	IRU	M18-M36

Table 1 List of Tasks in Work Package 6

The focus on WP6 is to create an impact in terms of communication, dissemination, and exploitation, including standardisation. The AITHENA project will be communicated, the achievements will be disseminated, and the results will be exploited according to the communication, dissemination and exploitation including standardisation plan which form the core of this deliverable as well as further update (M18).

2.1. Task 6.1 Communication strategy

This task coordinates the work in WP6 and monitors the progress in accordance with the project timeline. In addition, T6.1 will continuously liaise with the other WPs to ensure alignment of the project output with the project dissemination. A communication and dissemination strategy will be developed, identifying the knowledge to be disseminated, the target audiences to be addressed and the channels used to maximise the reach of the knowledge generated in the project. The relevant scientific and industrial fora to be addressed will be defined and a timeline for the exchange with those fora will be set. The project identity will be defined by providing tools and guidelines for the project dissemination.

2.2. Task 6.2 Scientific and industrial dissemination and standardisation

This task will connect with the relevant scientific and industrial fora and events to disseminate the tools and knowledge generated in the project to an expert audience. The work will start with the identification of requirements and barriers for industry deployment of the developed solutions, to set the priorities for the content output. With regards to the exchange with the scientific community, the T6.2 aims to make the project output accessible via the publication of scientific papers and presentations at relevant conferences. In addition, a series of yearly practitioners' workshops will be organized to allow an in-depth exchange on the tools and methods.

2.3. Task 6.3 End user dissemination

The core of T6.3 will be an information campaign which aims to educate users about the use cases developed in the project and promote the advantages XAI in CCAM can bring to the users. To provide relevant information, the content of the campaign will be aligned with the user groups and user needs defined in T1.4. The campaign will use a two-pronged approach: the task will join public events to disseminate the developed information via printed materials, presentations and an exhibition of the test-rig developed in T3.3, allowing users to gather first-hand insights into AI processes in a CCAM vehicle. In addition, an online campaign will reach users via social media, using the channels of the project partners and the extensive reach of the FIA Region I Mobility Clubs.

2.4. WP6 – staff effort per partner

All 17 AITHENA partners have been allocated with resources for WP6 activities and will be supporting, in addition to those who lead and contribute to dedicated tasks in WP6, the communication, dissemination, and standardisation activities.

Participant	WP6 effort (Person-Month)
1 - VICOM	7.00
2 - IKA	2.30
3 - TUE	2.00
4 - VIF	2.00
5 - CAF	2.00
6 - TTTA	1.00
7 – SIE-NL	4.00
8 – SIE-BE	1.00
9 - IDI	4.00
10 - RC	11.00
11 - TNO	2.20
12 - MAPTM	1.00
13 - BUW	3.00
14 - IFAG	3.50
15 - VALEO	4.50
16 - FIA	19.60
17 - IRU	9.00

Table 2 Staff effort per participant in WP6

2.5. Interactions between WP6 and other WPs in AITHENA project

WP6 ensures that all Work Packages in AITHENA project are aligned when it comes to creating the impact of communication, dissemination, and exploitation, including standardisation activities.

Figure 2 Inter-relation between WPs

2.6. Intended audience of this deliverable

The communication, and dissemination plan has a particular purpose to support the overall strategy to maximise the impact of the AITHENA project, to increase the visibility of the project, and to ensure that the results and outputs reach a wide audience of relevant to the project stakeholders, also beyond the lifetime of the project itself.

This deliverable is a public report, and it will be made available for the public on the AITHENA website. This document for AITHENA consortium partners provides guidelines for the use of the available communications and dissemination tools and inform the consortium about procedures to be followed. For any other audience (externals to the consortium), it provides an overview of the AITHENA project objectives and purposes when it comes to communication, dissemination, and standardisation activities.

3. Work Package 6 - milestones and deliverables

3.1. Tasks 6.1-6.3 related deliverables

There are three deliverables which address Tasks 6.1-6.3 and are closely related to AITHENA communication, dissemination, and standardisation activities.

Deliverable	Type	Due date	Dissemination level	Lead beneficiary
D6.1 Initial communication, dissemination, and standardisation plan	R - Document, report	M6	PU - Public	16-FIA
D6.5 Report on dissemination and standardisation activities	R - Document, report	M36	PU - Public	16-FIA
D6.6 Updated communication, disseminations, and standardisation plan	R - Document, report	M18	PU - Public	16-FIA

Table 3 Tasks 6.1-6.3 related deliverables

3.2. Tasks 6.1-6.3 related milestones

There are four milestones which relate to Tasks 6.1-6.3.

Milestone No	Milestone name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)
6	Practitioner's workshop (year 1)	WP6	16-FIA	Event with stakeholders and experts	M12
10	Practitioner's workshop (year 2)	WP6	16-FIA	Event with stakeholders and experts	M24
15	Exploitation and standardisation plan agreed	WP6	16-FIA	To be reported in D6.1	M36
16	Practitioner's workshop (year 3)	WP6	16-FIA	Event with stakeholders and experts	M36

Table 4 Tasks 6.1-6.3 related milestones

4. Communication, dissemination, and standardisation plan

4.1. Objectives

The AITHENA communication and dissemination plan will set out a strategy to maximise the impact of the project, to increase its visibility, and to ensure that the project outputs reach a wide audience of relevant stakeholders.

The AITHENA consortium partners represent large groups of relevant organisations, and special focus of the project will be put on connecting with networks and communication channels that all AITHENA partners already have, through their affiliations and relations also via digital channels (newsletters, social media channels etc.). To create impact in terms of communication, dissemination, and exploitation, including standardisation, AITHENA's plan will:

- Create visibility for the project output and exchange with stakeholders' community to maximise the project's impact.
- Educate users about AI applications in CCAM through an online information campaign.
- Map existing XAI standards and identify gaps in standardisation needs.
- Develop guidelines and tools to encourage privacy-preserving AI development and testing processes.
- Give policy recommendations for exploitation of XAI in CCAM based on collected lessons learned.
- Conduct an analysis of business models employing XAI in CCAM.
- Contribute to common information, dissemination activities, and synergies between HE/H2020 supported actions.

4.1.1. Purpose

The main purpose of the plan is to improve current AI development introducing trustworthiness concept from the beginning in all the dimension of AI system implementation: design, development, deployment, and operational phases. And to raise awareness of the importance of creation of explainable AI solutions to speed up the development and deployment process of AI solutions in the field.

4.2. Key messages

Key messages will be extracted from all recommendations and guidelines developed in the project (*T6.5 Lessons learned and policy recommendations*) ensuring brief and impactful considerations can be communicated, which will result in creating interest for the detailed AITHENA results to be disseminated among relevant stakeholders. An analysis of lessons learned will provide basis for developing policy recommendations for AI's solutions' exploitation in CCAM with focus on practical guidance for authorities and stakeholders on planning and implementing AI solutions. Consequently, the recommendations will be translated into key messages for users and disseminated via AITHENA channels, with support of consortium partners to reach wide range of relevant networks and stakeholders.

Additionally, AI and CCAM related relevant key messages will be extracted from existing resources and complemented with visual materials that will be created specifically for the AITHENA project.

Specifically, an information campaign, as a core of *T6.3 End user dissemination*, will be implemented. The campaign, which main aim is to educate users about the AITHENA use cases developed in WP1 and to promote the advantages XAI in CCAM can bring to users. The key messages will be prepared in collaboration with *T1.4 Identification of user group needs and definition of use cases* which will provide user groups and user needs identifications. To ensure wide reach of the AITHENA campaign, the project presence will be made via consortium partners at public events to disseminate developed information and outcomes (presentations, panel discussions, dedicated sessions organised, technical and scientific papers, and posters). Dissemination of the AITHENA key messages will be also supported by exhibition of the test-rig developed in *T3.3 Transparent edge-case training using mixed real-synthetic data*. The campaign built around key messages will allow users to gather first-hands insights into AI processes in a CCAM vehicle. The AITHENA education campaign for users with project physical presence will be complemented by online campaign via project’s social media channels as well as channels of AITHENA consortium partners.

4.3. Implementation phases

The communication, dissemination, and exploitation (including standardisation) plan will be structured into three main phases aligned with the AITHENA lifetime:

- Awareness building phase.
- Participation phase.
- Action phase.

Figure 3 AITHENA phases

4.4. Target audience, channels, and messages

The initial analysis proposed by consortium partners has identified the following AITHENA target groups, pathways and channels, and key messages and means to be used.

Target group	Pathways and channels	Key messages and means
Technical experts, and scientific community	Events, scientific congresses, journal papers, dedicated workshops	XAI can be applied to CCAM. AITHENA's novel XAI and data management methods obtain satisfactory performance results.
CCAM value chain	Events, meetings, dedicated workshops, webinars, congresses, website, social media	AITHENA harmonised XAI methodology addresses all driving subsystems (perception, prediction, and decision) and improves trustworthiness.
Public	Social media, popular magazines	Reliability of AI based solutions thanks to the trustworthiness and explainable approach proposed by AITHENA -raise public acceptance
Standardisation	Dedicated workshops and meetings, interoperability, and compliance events	Demonstration of real-world usage and recommendations for CCAM XAI adoption. Integration of ongoing and new standards in project activities with focus on data management
Authorities / certification bodies	Events, specialized workshops with each of the main actors in the adoption of AITHENA methodology: authorities, certification, standardisation bodies. Dedicated workshops and user centred activities will be organized to provide insight in the X-AI approach and adoption of methodologies for CCAM	Testing and Validation approaches: Validation procedures can be improved adopting AITHENA's approach. Lessons learnt about the application of XAI in CCAM: limitations and ethical considerations. Standardization and certification: AITHENA methodology development and adoption – specific use case analysis and demos Application cases and use cases for local public authorities for considering ethics and explainability requirements for current and future CCAM solution and services to be deployed

Table 5 AITHENA Target audiences

5. Communication and dissemination procedures

5.1. EU disclaimer and emblem

Beneficiaries of the EU funding must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and provide funding statement in all communication and dissemination materials (both printed and digital versions). Therefore, all AITHENA activities related to communication and dissemination (presentations, papers, website, social media channels, publications etc.) will acknowledge the EU funding and fulfil the requirements¹ by including the funding disclaimer:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

and the EU emblem:

All necessary requirements will be communicated to the AITHENA consortium partners and guidelines will be provided to ensure that the acknowledgement of the EU funding is always followed.

5.2. Scientific and industrial dissemination, and standardisation plans - introduction

The goal of the scientific, industrial dissemination and standardisation activities is to publish AITHENA relevant results at scientific conferences that have a high impact factor in the machine learning and computer vision community. The consortium partners have initially identified the following typical representatives:

- IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR).
- IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV).
- European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV).
- IEEE/CVF Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW).

¹ [Communicating your project — Acknowledgement of EU funding - Online Manual - Funding Tenders Opportunities \(europa.eu\)](#)

Furthermore, relevant project results will be incorporated into standardization efforts to increase the impact of what has been achieved in the AITHENA project. The identification of concrete standardization bodies as well as project results worthy of standardization will be done during the project's implementation.

5.3. Yearly practitioners' workshops

The AITHENA project aims at organising workshops that could be held in conjunction with relevant conferences, congresses, or other relevant events. The topic of the workshop could be related to "Trustworthy and Explainable AI". Project partners will aim for conferences that have a high reputation and belong to the computer vision and machine learning domain, e.g., the IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium. For this purpose, a successful application process must be passed, and the best workshop concept must prevail from many applicants.

Part of the practitioners' workshop will consist of interesting talks and presentations by well-known speakers in the safe AI and computer vision domain. Furthermore, a call for papers will be organized, where publications in the relevant topic area for AITHENA can be submitted. The paper process will be peer-reviewed and double-blind. Accepted publications will be published in the conference proceedings and presented in the form of orals and posters on the workshop day. To round out the AITHENA practitioners' workshop experience, a panel discussion with selected experts will be envisioned to address pressing issues facing the AITHENA project.

6. Communication tools and techniques

All communication tools and techniques to communicate about the project are described in the following paragraphs. A branding guideline has been developed that incorporates the style and colours based on the logo prepared for the AITHENA project.

6.1. Visual identity and branding guidelines

The visual identity and branding guidelines will be the base for all communication output material. This way, a cohesive branding will be used when communicating about the AITHENA project. All the following materials are shared and made available to all partners in the project.

6.1.1. Logo

The following are the logos of the project. It comes in a vertical and horizontal format. The logos are also available different colours, as shown below, to match light and dark coloured backgrounds.

6.1.2. Colours

The colour palette of the project's branding are the following three variants of blue.

The main colour is a dark blue (with the following colour reference codes: CMYK 100-92-42-47, RGB 22-30-67, #161E43).

The two secondary colours are two lighter blues. The brighter blue or cyan blue has the following colour reference codes: CMYK 100-92-42-47, RGB 3-241-255, #03F1FF. The last blue or majorelle blue has the following colour reference codes: CMYK 83-58-0-0, RGB 3-109-255, #036DFF.

	DARK BLUE CMYK 100-92-42-47 RGB 22-30-67 #161E43
	CYAN CMYK 100-92-42-47 RGB 3-241-255 #03F1FF
	MAJORELLE BLUE CMYK 83-58-0-0 RGB 3-109-255 #036DFF

6.1.3. Fonts

The main fonts for project outputs are Muli in Light, Regular, and Semi-bold, and Franklin Gothic in Medium. The Muli font will be used for all body text while the Franklin Gothic font will be used for Headings.

<p>Muli</p> <hr/> <p>Is the typo of the Althena logo. This is the typeface to be used for body text.</p>	<p>Aa light</p> <p>Aa regular</p> <p>Aa semibold</p>
<p>Franklin Gothic Medium</p> <hr/> <p>It will be used for Headings</p>	<p>Aa regular</p>

6.1.4. Templates (presentation, deliverable)

Document templates for reports and presentations in the form of a Word document and a PowerPoint files have been shared with all partners to use. Partners will use these templates when communicating about the AITHENA project. Screenshots of the documents are shared below.

Figure 4 AITHENA PowerPoint presentation template

Figure 5 AITHENA deliverable, report Word template

6.2. Website

The AITHENA project website will use the domain www.aithena.eu and will be the public facing area where all public information about the project will be shared.

Other domains have also been purchased and will be redirected to www.aithena.eu to gather all interested parties in the project to one website. The purpose of this is also to avoid similar domains being used that may have no link to the project.

The other domains purchased are www.aithena-project.eu, www.horizonproject-aithena.eu and www.project-aithena.eu.

6.2.1. Purpose

The purpose of the website is to have a place where all public information about the AITHENA project can be stored, shared, and promoted. The website is a communication channel for project's visibility and database for all relevant information about the project's progress, the partners involved, and the aim of the project.

6.2.2. Structure

The draft structure of the website includes one landing page or the home page, five sub-pages including an About page, a Partners page, a News & Events page, a Library page, and a Contact page.

A screenshot of the draft homepage with the top menu is available below.

Figure 6 Screenshot of AITHENA website draft (homepage)

The *Home page* will include a short introduction of the AITHENA project, a video about the AITHENA project, a news section, and a short boiler plate about the AITHENA project and a box with contact information and icons to the project's social media platforms.

The *About page* will include a longer text about the AITHENA project.

The *Partners page* will have all the logos of the partners.

The *News & Events page* will have all the latest information, such as blogs, articles and events related to the AITHENA project.

The *Library page* will be an area for downloads of items such as public deliverables and reports, scientific and technical publications, or campaign materials.

The *Contact page* will include details on how to contact the coordination teams responsible for the AITHENA project.

6.3. Social media channels

Two social media accounts will be developed for the AITHENA project. These will be on Twitter and LinkedIn. The purpose of these accounts is to communicate about the project to the public, promote and disseminate the AITHENA project results and outputs to reach organizations and stakeholders who are interested in AI and CCAM technologies.

The social media accounts will be updated on a regular basis dependent on the input from the projects and all partners in the project. There would be at least one post per week on Twitter and one post per week on LinkedIn. The frequency of publishing considered content on AITHENA social media accounts can be re-evaluated upon the level of activity relevant to the project during specific periods.

Both social media channels have been already established and appropriate content to what has been done or planned in AITHENA project was already published on channels.

6.3.1. LinkedIn page

The LinkedIn account² handle is @Aithena.

Partners will need to follow the account and can use the account as a platform to share updates about the project's progress or events where the project is mentioned. The LinkedIn account will be managed by the FIA, Work Package 6 leader, and content will be provided by all partners.

² <https://www.linkedin.com/company/aithena-eu-project/>

Figure 7 Screenshot of AITHENA LinkedIn page

6.3.2. Twitter account

The Twitter account³ handle is @_Althena_.

Partners will need to follow the account and can use the account as a platform to share updates about the project's progress or events where the project is mentioned. The Twitter account will be managed by the FIA, Work Package 6 leader, and content will be provided by all partners.

³ https://twitter.com/Althena_

Figure 8 Screenshot of AITHENA Twitter account

6.4. Newsletters

The newsletter for the AITHENA project will be established using a dedicated tool and a registration form will be integrated into the public website. The newsletter will have low frequency for the first 12 months of the project and will be sent on regular basis (estimated 3 times a year) as from M13 of the project implementation. The newsletter will be sent out when there is important information to be shared about the project. This can include events, new publications, and other relevant information about the project's development.

The newsletter will be distributed via the website's system and will follow all general data protection rules. Newsletters will not be sent out without prior and agreed consent of the recipients receiving the newsletter.

6.5. Communication materials (printed and digital)

6.5.1. Flyer, leaflet, brochure

The AITHENA project coordinator, VICOMTECH, will prepare the leaflet, flyer, and/or brochure design for the project. Partners will be encouraged to print these materials when needed (physical events, internal communication etc.). Digital versions will also be made available to reduce the likelihood of wasting printed material. It will also allow to easily adapt and updated the content. The materials will highlight the objectives of the project, the consortium, and any other relevant content for which the materials will be prepared.

6.5.2. Roll-up

The AITHENA roll-up will be prepared, and it will be printed for the purpose of visibility at events, conferences, or other physical occasions with the project presence. There will be a digital version of the roll-up and all partners will be encouraged to print (if needed) and adjust the content for their purpose.

The roll-up will follow the AITHENA guidelines, and it will include the project title, logo (and other design), objectives of the project, the consortium (logo of all partners), the website and social media channels.

6.5.3. Poster

A generic poster about the AITHENA project will be prepared and can be used and printed by project partners primarily when attending conferences, congresses, and other relevant external events where the project is presented.

6.5.4. Videos

An introductory video about the AITHENA project has been already developed by VICOMTECH, the coordinator. This video has been shared on AITHENA social media channels and shorter versions are also available (more suitable for content on social media), and AITHENA partners can use the video in their presentations about the project. The video will be made publicly available on the project website.

An additional video will be created in the later stage of the project (M36), with the project results and achievements. Both videos will be targeted at the public and media. Additional videos might be created based on the needs of the project.

6.5.5. Press releases and articles

Press releases and articles about the AITHENA project will be prepared by partners involved in specific conferences, events, or activities. These will then be proofread and edited by FIA, Work Package 6 leader and shared with VICOMTECH for approval before publishing on the website (especially for press releases).

6.5.6. Information campaign

An information campaign will be led and carried out by WP6 leader, FIA, with support from all remaining partners in Work Package 6. Support can come in the form of shared inputs for messages of the campaign, and results that can be easily understood by target audiences.

The details of the information campaign will be defined at a later stage of the project when preliminary results have been identified. The campaign (part of *T6.3 End user dissemination*) aims to educate users about the use cases developed in the project and to promote the advantages XAI in CCAM can bring to the users.

7. Conferences and events

7.1. Identified relevant events

An initial list of relevant, both European and international conferences, workshops and other external (to the consortium) events has been identified and includes the following:

- IEEE International Conference on Service Oriented Computing and Applications
- IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
- International Simulation Conference
- ITS European and World congresses
- IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems
- IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference
- European Conference on Connected and Automated Driving
- Transport Research Arena conference
- Conference on Results from road Transport Research.

The list of relevant conferences and events will be available for all partners, and new, applicable to the scope of AITHENA project, items will be added to the list. External events and meetings will be used to present the project to a wider audience, to interact with different group of stakeholders, and to validate (if relevant) project results and outcomes.

All AITHENA partners are encouraged to communicate and disseminate the project and its findings via presentations, speaking slots, organisation of sessions, exhibitions, presentation of posters and papers. Partners will be required to inform the WP6 leader, FIA, about any external activities' participation, and report on performed activities.

8. Monitoring and recording of project activities

8.1. Dissemination and communication channels and KPIs

The table presents the Key Performance Indicators for communication and dissemination channels that have been initially identified.

Online channels (website and social media)			
Key indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Material downloads	< 50	50 – 150	> 150
Relevant contacts made through online channel	< 10	10 - 20	> 20

Conferences, workshops, and webinars			
Key indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Number of conferences	< 6	6 - 10	> 10
Number of people reached per event	< 50	50 - 150	> 150

Clustering with other projects, networking, and international initiatives			
Key indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Number of projects and/or activities	< 3	4 - 7	> 8

Scientific and technical publications			
Key indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Number of articles accepted by peer-reviewed journals	< 2	3 - 5	> 6
Number of blog entries	< 4	5 - 10	> 10
Newsletter contact list	< 100	100 - 300	> 300

Project videos			
Key indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact
Number of viewers of videos	< 100	100 - 1000	> 1000

Table 6 Dissemination and communication channels and KPIs

8.2. Communication and dissemination register

An excel table which serves as a register for all communication, dissemination, and standardization activities which will be performed during the implementation of the AITHENA project, has been prepared and made available to all partners on AITHENA SharePoint/Teams. The register will play twofold role, on one side as a repository of all activities relevant to communication, and dissemination of the project. On the other side it will be used as a supporting document for the final reporting period and be part of the report/deliverable *D6.5 Report on dissemination and standardization activities* (M36).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
	Nº	Month of project	Date	1)booth, stand (exhibition), 2)participation in/speaking at a conference, congress, 3)organisation, participation in a special session, 4)participation in a workshop, 5)participation in other events, 6)participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s), initiatives, 7)other activity	Type of event	Title of event	Location	Title of presentation, panel discussion, session etc.	Responsible partner	Involved partners	Type of audience	No of participants	Description
1													
2	1	5	08/03/2023	5	IRU members meeting update	CTP meeting (Passenger transport meeting)	Brussels	Research & Innovation update	IRU			IRU passenger transport members	30
3	2	6	16-19/04/2023	2	International event	Automotive Week 2023. Smart. Sustainable. Safe.	Helmond, the Netherlands	Key note speech by Margriet van Schijndel - de Nooij					

Figure 9 Screenshot of the AITHENA register file.

9. Scientific publications

AITHENA will make all scientific publications stemming from the conducted research available through gold or green open access. We will select the most appropriate journal for each specific paper. Examples of relevant peer-reviewed journals that have been already identified by the AITHENA consortium include:

- IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence
- Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory
- IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering
- IEEE Open Journal of ITS
- IEEE Transactions on ITS
- IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles
- IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology.

Moreover, scientific conferences will be excellent platforms to disseminate our findings and start direct conversations with the audience.

9.1. Open Science

AITHENA project will contribute to the European vision “Open innovation, open science, open to the world”⁴ which represents an innovative approach to the scientific process based on cooperative work and new ways of diffusing knowledge by using digital technologies and new collaborative tools.

AITHENA partners will be encouraged to support publications of scientific papers and generated datasets to open access journals and repositories as zenodo.org⁵ and the European Open Science Cloud⁶, which provide open access to scientific publications and the research outcomes following the FAIR guiding principles (making results *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable* – see *Data Management Plan*). As for the publication strategies that aims to disseminate and exploit the scientific achievements of the project:

- On publication of foreground: The Parties are encouraged to publish the material related to the public deliverables of the project. All partners will be responsible for publishing project results, in local and international press, and in peer-reviewed scientific journals and at conferences.
- On the access to knowledge: The principal interface for knowledge access, both internally and externally, will primarily be achieved through the AITHENA website which will contain the public deliverables as well as the list of scientific publications with the external link. The partner will be requested to create a profile on a repository (e.g., Zenodo) to pursuit the dissemination of Gold Open Access publications.
- Publication guidelines: The consortium, following the GA regulations and IPR, is encouraged to publish on ISI journals the project results with Gold and Green open access modalities. The project’s board of partners will define when data should not be published open access, and the WP6 Leader will monitor publications. Open access publications will be available in “Gold” open access, and budgets have been set aside accordingly.
- AITHENA Results: External collaboration through the Github (or similar) repositories.
- Datasets to be shared following Open Data and Data Lake principles (see T6.4).

⁴ [Open innovation, open science, open to the world | Shaping Europe’s digital future \(europa.eu\)](#)

⁵ [Zenodo - Research. Shared.](#)

⁶ [EOSC Portal \(eosc-portal.eu\)](#)

10. List of acronyms and terms

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CCAM	Cooperative Automotive Mobility
DX.X	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HE	Horizon Europe
H2020	Horizon 2020
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MX.X	Milestone
TX.X	Task
RIA	Research and Innovation Actions
WP	Work Package
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence